

Nuclear Data Uncertainty Quantification for Small High-Leakage Light Water Reactors using CASMO5/SIMULATE5

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ABSTRACT

Recently, nuclear data Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) has been implemented into CASMO5. This work exercises this new UQ capability by propagating uncertainties from CASMO5 to SIMULATE5, as well as extending previous analysis by applying nuclear data UQ to the Otto Hahn critical experiment. The propagation of uncertainties to SIMULATE5 using the forward statistical sampling approach is achieved by applying perturbations to the CASMO5 nuclear data library, based on covariance data, and performing lattice calculations for all assembly types used in the construction of the SIMULATE5 library. The resulting set of perturbed libraries, containing homogenized data, are subsequently used by SIMULATE5. Predicted standard deviations show excellent agreement between the transport-based CASMO5 reference calculation and two-step CASMO5/SIMULATE5 results. It is observed that fission rate uncertainties can strongly depend on the number of energy groups used in the neutron transport solution. The CASMO5/SIMULATE5-predicted eigenvalue standard deviation for the full core Otto Hahn critical experiment is 616 pcm. Fission rate distribution uncertainties are also presented.

Keywords: CASMO5, SIMULATE5, Uncertainty Quantification, Covariance

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, nuclear data Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) has been implemented into CASMO5 [1,2], which is Studsvik's advanced lattice physics code for Light Water Reactors (LWR) analysis. The ability to perform UQ from nuclear data uncertainties is a significant leap in the analysis capabilities available in Studsvik's Core Management System 5 (CMS5) [3], which is composed of CASMO5 and SIMULATE5. The initial motivation for developing nuclear data UQ in CASMO5 stemmed from the need to assess decay heat uncertainties [2,4], which involved comparisons to decay heat measurements, as well as quantifying the effect of the uncertainties on disposal canister loading scenarios. More recently, the existing UQ capability in CASMO5 was exercised in the evaluation of integral index c_k , also referred to as the similarity index, between various applications and experiments involving enrichments greater than the current 5 wt.% limit and high burnup [5]. Thus far, the application of UQ in CASMO5 has been limited to single- and multi-assembly (MxN) calculations within the same lattice physics code system. However, it is possible to propagate the nuclear data uncertainty for downstream use by SIMULATE5 given the forward statistical sampling approach [6,7].

Interest in extending the licensing of CMS5 to enrichments greater than the current 5 wt.% limit, as well as Small Modular Reactors (SMR) in a generic fashion, has motivated recent CMS5 benchmarking efforts. Benchmarking CMS5 against extended enrichment critical experiments [8], comparisons to reference Monte Carlo solutions [9,10], as well as validation against the Otto Hahn critical experiment [11], validates the applicability of the code system to new LWR fuel assembly and core designs. The Otto Hahn critical experiment is particularly relevant to this work, as it involves Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) 17 × 17 fuel assemblies with greater than 5 wt.% enrichment and a small high-leakage core configuration.

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The goal of the work presented here is to exercise the current UQ capabilities by propagating uncertainties from CASMO5 to SIMULATE5, as well as extending previous analysis [11] by applying nuclear data UQ to the Otto Hahn critical experiment using CMS5. The propagation of uncertainties to SIMULATE5 using the forward statistical sampling approach is achieved by applying perturbations to the CASMO5 nuclear data library, based on covariance data, and performing lattice calculations for all assembly types used in the construction of the SIMULATE5 library. The resulting set of perturbed libraries, containing homogenized data, are subsequently used by SIMULATE5.

To verify the impact of the two-step procedure on predicted eigenvalue and fission rate distribution uncertainties, a comparison between uncertainties from CASMO5 MxN and SIMULATE5 two-dimensional calculations is presented in this work. Uncertainties derived from the MxN calculation, which relies on the solution of the neutron transport equation using the Method of Characteristics (MoC), are used as references to assess the predicted uncertainties from using the SIMULATE5 spatially homogenized, few-group diffusion theory solution. The small core configuration, as well as the use of fresh fuel assemblies, makes the use of forward statistical sampling amenable from a computational perspective.

The rest of this work is organized as follows. An overview of the CASMO5 nuclear data uncertainty quantification methods and covariance library is presented in Section 2.1. Similarly, a description of the forward stochastic sampling used to propagate the perturbations from CASMO5 to downstream SIMULATE5 is presented in Section 2.2. Numerical results involving eigenvalue and fission rate distribution uncertainties are presented in Section 3, along with a comparison of uncertainties predicted by the MxN calculations and SIMULATE5. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section 4.

2. METHODOLOGY

The nuclear data uncertainty quantification method implemented in CMS5 relies on covariance data provided by evaluators in standard library files such as recent ENDF/B releases. As described in the next sub-section, forward stochastic sampling treats the existing physics models as a black box, and only the inputs to the models need to be perturbed. This sampling approach is attractive, as it requires minimal changes to the code system. The drawback from stochastic sampling is the requirement of sufficient samples to be instantiated to achieve sufficiently converged uncertainties. The propagation of perturbations from CASMO5 to SIMULATE5, which is also described below, is straightforward if perturbations are consistently applied to all supporting lattice physics calculations.

2.1. Nuclear Data Uncertainty Methods

Given a covariance matrix C and a k -vector \vec{x} , the probability density function (pdf) is

$$f(\vec{x}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^k |C|}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} (\vec{x} - \vec{x}_0)^T C^{-1} (\vec{x} - \vec{x}_0) \right] , \quad (1)$$

where $|C|$ is the determinant of C and \vec{x}_0 is the expected value. Sampling the multivariate distribution above requires defining a matrix A such that $C = A A^T$. Computing A is achieved by applying Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) to the covariance matrix such that

$$C = U \Sigma V^T = U \Sigma U^T . \quad (2)$$

Since C is symmetric, then $C = C^T$. Using the SVD of matrix C , then A can be found

$$A = U \sqrt{\Sigma} . \quad (3)$$

Noting that Σ is a diagonal matrix, computing the square root is trivial. Vector \vec{x} can now be sampled using

$$\vec{x}_i = \vec{x}_0 + A \vec{z}_i , \quad (4)$$

where \vec{z}_i is a vector with elements that are independently sampled from a standard normal distribution. Note that matrix A is referred to as the sampling matrix, which is what is stored in the pre-processed CASMO5 covariance library.

Perturbations on the cross sections are achieved by defining a multiplier m_i , such that $x_i = m_i \cdot x_0$. The sampling equation is now written as follows

$$M^{-1} \vec{x}_i = M^{-1} \vec{x}_0 + M^{-1} A \vec{z}_i \quad , \quad (5)$$

where M is a diagonal matrix with the vector \vec{x}_0 as the diagonal. The final multiplier vector is

$$\vec{m}_i = M^{-1} A \vec{z}_i + \vec{1} \quad . \quad (6)$$

Although the sampling derived above assumes absolute covariances, the CASMO5 implementation uses the correlation matrix, which provides improved numerical stability when performing the SVD procedure. A list of the data perturbed in the CASMO5 library is shown in Table I.

Table I. MT numbers for reaction types available to sample. Some MTs are non-standard.

MT	Symbol	Description
13	σ_s	Scatter XS
16	σ_{2n}	$(n, 2n)$ XS
18	σ_f	Fission XS
101	σ_d	Disappearance (including (n, γ) , (n, α) , etc.)
452	ν	Neutrons per fission
457	λ	Decay constants
458	κ	Energy release per fission
459	FY	Fission yields
461	DBR	Branch ratios for decay
462	CBR	Branch ratios for capture
1018	χ	Fission spectrum

The ENDF/B-VIII.0 covariance data files were processed using the NJOY-2016 ERRORR module. The resulting relative covariance matrices, as well as nominal cross sections, were formatted in a manner suitable for the multi-group CASMO5 covariance library. This covariance library is read only once at the beginning of the calculation, the sampling computed, and the perturbation saved and applied throughout the rest of the CASMO5 calculation.

Multiplicative perturbations are defined as follows

$$\sigma'_{xg} = m_{xg} \sigma_{xg} \quad , \quad (6)$$

where x and g denote the reaction rate and energy group, respectively. The covariance library contains multi-group covariances in a 95-group structure, which is a subset of the CASMO5 586 energy-group library structure. This allows for straightforward mapping between the library fine groups and coarse perturbation groups, hence avoiding remapping of disparate energy group structures.

2.2. Propagation of Perturbations using Two-Step Procedure

Recalling the two-step procedure, a set of single-assembly calculations are performed to generate a single homogenized data library for use by the downstream full-core calculation. In the forward statistical sampling method, a set of N perturbed data are generated based on covariances and single-assembly calculations are performed N number of times. Therefore, given an instance of perturbed data, each single-assembly calculation needed to generate a homogenized data library is performed using perturbed data, thereby yielding a perturbed library for use by the full-core calculation. Hence, one can generate N perturbed homogenized data libraries in which each constituent single-assembly case is consistently perturbed using the same perturbed data.

The resulting set of N perturbed libraries are used by N full-core calculations and uncertainties in predicted quantities obtained by performing basic statistics on output quantities. This procedure is depicted in Figure 1, where CASMO5 lattices, also known as segments, are denoted as SEG. A set of N SIMULATE5 calculations are performed, and the resulting uncertainties are obtained from these calculations.

Figure 1. Diagram of propagation of perturbations using two-step procedure. Lattices, also known as segments, are denoted as SEG. The perturbations and homogenized libraries are denoted as PERT and LIB, respectively.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

All numerical results use the ENDF/B-VII.1-based e7r1.202.586.bin data library and ENDF/B-VIII.0-based cov.e8r0.95.20231026.bin covariance library for the nuclear data UQ. As noted in prior publications [1], one exception is the Pu-239 (n, γ) variance data which is drawn from the ENDF/B-VII.1 evaluation. A thousand perturbed samples ($N = 1000$) are used for all the CASMO5 (C5) Single Assembly (SA) and MxN calculations, as well as all SIMULATE5 (S5) calculations.

3.1. Otto Hahn Critical Experiment

The Otto Hahn nuclear ship program created small pressurized LWRs for propulsion of civilian ships. As part of the program, the second core was tested for subcriticality at cold conditions. One of these tests, the configuration with the control rods completely withdrawn, is recorded in Ref. [12]. The central assemblies consist of 3.5 wt.% enriched fuel, whereas periphery assemblies consist of 6.6 wt.% enriched fuel. Burnable poison pins are present and are composed of ZrO_2 and ZrB_2 . In full symmetry, twelve 17×17 assemblies are arranged with a small number of fuel pins in the corners. The square pins in the assembly corners are structural supports. The core contains twelve fuel assemblies and four corner fuel assemblies. A depiction of the Otto Hahn core generated by C5 is shown in Figure 2. The axial buckling was obtained from a 3D Monte Carlo calculation [11] to model the core in two-dimensional geometry.

Each corner assembly contains four oversized rods, which consist of fuel and B_4C absorber core. The pitch of these rods are 1.5 times the regular pin pitch. The cladding outer diameter for the oversized fuel rod with a B_4C core is approximated to fit inside a regular lattice pitch location in the C5 model. The annular region containing helium is ignored, and the cladding inner diameter is set to be equal to the fuel region outer diameter. The cladding outer diameter is set to be equal to the pin pitch. Then, cladding number densities are adjusted to preserve the total mass. The reactor core is surrounded by borated-water moderator, and the reflector tank is not modeled.

Figure 2. Otto Hahn core geometry generated by C5.

The cross-section data for the S5 models are generated from single-assembly C5 calculations with reflective boundary conditions using either 19 or 95 energy groups. In addition to assembly-homogenized data, submesh (SMX) data are generated from single assembly calculations using a default 5x5 SMX layout of a quarter PWR assembly. The SMX model in S5 is used to correct assembly homogenized cross-sections and discontinuity factors for the change in the intra-assembly flux shape used in single assembly calculations versus the flux shape in the actual core, which is substantial for a high leakage, small core such as the Otto Hahn core. Details on the CMS5 results are found in Ref. [11].

3.2. Uncertainties from Reference and Two-Step Calculations

Three configurations for the verification phase were considered. The first configuration considers the Otto Hahn 6.6 wt.% enriched assembly in an infinite lattice configuration. The second configuration considers only the Otto Hahn core as a color-set problem with 3.5 wt.% fuel in the southeast corner with the reflector removed. The third configuration considers the two-dimensional core geometry depicted in Figure 2.

A comparison of the predicted eigenvalue uncertainty in terms of Standard Deviation (SD) versus sample number, as well as percent Relative SD (%RSD) of the fuel pin-averaged Fission Rate (FR) distribution is presented below for the three configurations in Figure 3 through Figure 5. For each configuration, the figures compare the eigenvalue and fission rate distribution uncertainties between C5 (either SA or MxN) versus the two-step method (C5/S5). For instance, the top row in Figure 3 depicts the eigenvalue SD between the reference C5 SA and C5/S5 results on the left and side-by-side comparison of the FR %RSD between C5 SA and C5/S5 results. The C5 reference results, as well as the SA calculation, use 19 energy groups (19g) in the MoC solution. All S5 results use 4 energy groups (4g). An analogous arrangement of results is depicted in the bottom row of Figure 3, but corresponds to using 95 energy groups (95g) for all the C5 calculations (including the two-step procedure.) This is repeated for the second and third configurations.

Excellent agreement is found for all three configurations between the reference and S5 predictions. Small FR %RSD are observed in these results and confirmed with values reported in the literature [7]. It is observed that FR uncertainties strongly depend on the number of energy groups used in the MoC solution, as shown by the difference in scales. Specifically, the Figure 3 and Figure 5 maximum FR %RSD are a factor of two greater for the C5 95g results relative to C5 19g predictions. As shown shortly, the reason the FR %RSD is close in magnitude between the C5 19g and 95g predictions in Figure 4 arises from the fact that the pin FR possessing the maximum %RSD is close in magnitude to the maximum pin FR, for which the FR %RSD is accurately predicted by both C5 19g and 95g calculations.

Table II provides a summary of the uncertainties in terms of SD. Excellent agreement is found for the eigenvalue SD for each configuration. The maximum FR SDs, tabulated in the sixth column, are in excellent agreement between the C5 SA, and MxN, relative to the values produced by the two-step procedure using C5/S5. As noted above, the maximum FR SD for the color-set case corresponds to an FR similar in magnitude to the maximum FR, hence the agreement between the 95g and 19g predictions. Finally, note that the FR SDs for the full core calculation strongly depend on the MoC energy groups. Nominal FR distributions are relatively insensitive to the number of groups.

Figure 3. Eigenvalue Standard Deviation (SD) and fission rate distribution percent Relative SD (%RSD) uncertainties for Otto Hahn 6.6 wt.% single assembly in lattice configuration.

Figure 4. Eigenvalue Standard Deviation (SD) and fission rate distribution percent Relative SD (%RSD) uncertainties for Otto Hahn core in color-set (3.5 wt.% fuel in southeast corner, reflector removed.)

Figure 5. Eigenvalue Standard Deviation (SD) and fission rate distribution percent Relative SD (%RSD) uncertainties for Otto Hahn 2D case.

Table II. Summary of Eigenvalue SD and FR SD for all configurations.

Configuration	Calculation	Groups	Eig. SD (pcm)	Max. SD pin		Max. FR pin	
				FR	SD	FR	SD
SA	C5 (SA)	19	674	0.814	0.0015	1.125	0.0009
	C5/S5	19/4	674	0.813	0.0015	1.125	0.0009
	C5 (SA)	95	685	0.810	0.0032	1.125	0.0009
	C5/S5	95/4	685	0.809	0.0032	1.125	0.0009
Color-set	C5 (MxN)	19	660	1.590	0.0053	1.590	0.0053
	C5/S5	19/4	660	1.583	0.0053	1.583	0.0053
	C5 (MxN)	95	670	1.146	0.0062	1.587	0.0053
	C5/S5	95/4	670	1.535	0.0059	1.583	0.0053
Full core	C5 (MxN)	19	607	1.487	0.0044	1.764	0.0021
	C5/S5	19/4	607	1.498	0.0044	1.761	0.0021
	C5 (MxN)	95	615	0.511	0.0097	1.768	0.0040
	C5/S5	95/4	616	0.536	0.0126	1.761	0.0039

4. CONCLUSIONS

Nuclear data UQ results for a small high-leakage core are presented in this work using the recently developed forward stochastic sampling method implemented in CASMO5. Propagation to SIMULATE5 is demonstrated by generating a set of homogenized data libraries. The UQ methods underpinning the CASMO5/SIMULATE5 are overviewed and results presented for the eigenvalue and fission rate distribution uncertainties for the Otto Hahn critical experiment. Predicted standard deviations show excellent agreement between the transport-based CASMO5 reference calculation and two-step CASMO5/SIMULATE5 results. It is observed that fission rate uncertainties can strongly depend on the number of energy groups used in the MoC solution. The CASMO5/SIMULATE5-predicted eigenvalue standard deviation for the full core Otto Hahn critical experiment is 616 pcm. The standard deviation for the pin with the maximum fission rate is 0.0039. The overall maximum fission rate standard deviation is 0.0126 and corresponds to the corner periphery pin. Full three-dimensional CASMO5/SIMULATE5 fission rate uncertainty distributions will be reported in future work.

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